

Mapping the neutron flux in the cavity of the CROCUS zero-power reactor with ^3He position-sensitive detectors

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20804186

ABSTRACT

In this work we present a preliminary investigation of the neutron distribution in the cavity, i.e., the internal space located between the reactor vessel and the concrete shielding, of the CROCUS zero-power reactor. This analysis is carried out using a ^3He position-sensitive proportional counter, which enables the determination of the positions of thermal neutron interactions along the active volume, and thus the reconstruction of the spatial distribution of neutrons in the sought region. The objective of this study is to experimentally quantify the shape and the magnitude of the neutron flux in the cavity surrounding the reactor, characterizing the spatial variations with increasing distance from the core center. Measurements are performed in two regions of the cavity: the upper part, extending from the fuel to the reactor ceiling, and the lateral part, spanning from the vessel wall to the cavity boundary.

Keywords: CROCUS zero-power reactor, ^3He proportional counters, ex-vessel measurements

1. INTRODUCTION

Extensive research at the CROCUS zero-power reactor (operated at EPFL, Switzerland) has focused on measuring the neutron flux inside the core, with studies ranging from the analysis of neutron noise induced by fuel oscillations [1] to intra-pin flux assessment [2]. A comprehensive overview of past experimental campaigns is provided in Ref. 3. By contrast, very limited information is available concerning the neutron distribution within the reactor cavity, i.e., the region outside the vessel but inside the concrete shielding that hosts the reactor core. To date, the only measurements involving the ex-vessel neutron flux consist of TLD data in the context of activation analysis. However, the investigation of such neutron field can be of particular interest for several reasons. First, it provides valuable experimental data for studying the shielding effects of the vessel and for assessing how structures external to the core can attenuate and distort the flux, including the contribution of back-scattering from the surrounding walls and ceiling. Second, it provides ex-vessel experimental data that could prove useful for the validation of Monte Carlo simulation codes, an aspect of growing interest in the context of reactor dosimetry and fluence calculations [4,5].

In this work, we present a preliminary mapping of the CROCUS zero-power reactor cavity, performed using a position-sensitive ^3He detector to measure the neutron flux in the region above and around the core. This paper is organized as follows: in Sec. 2 we describe the experimental setup; in Sec. 3 we present the results of the measurements performed in the upper part of the cavity, above the core, while in Sec. 4 we show the results for the lateral part. Finally, in Sec. 5 we discuss the possible applications of these measurements, with particular emphasis on their use for the validation of Monte Carlo simulation codes.

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2. EXPERIMENTAL AND MEASUREMENT SETUP

CROCUS is a light-water-moderated reactor licensed to operate up to a maximum thermal power of 100 W. The core contains two types of fuel rods, distributed in two interlocking zones: the inner zone, which includes 336 uranium dioxide fuel rods enriched at 1.806 wt.%, and the outer zone, which consists of a variable number of metallic uranium fuel rods enriched at 0.947 wt.%. The number of rods in the outer zone can be adjusted depending on the specific experimental configuration, and it currently includes 180 rods for hosting the SAFFRON array detection system [6, 7]. The cylindrical vessel wall consists of aluminum, with an inner radius of 65 cm and a wall thickness of 1.2 cm, and is contained in a larger tank structure. In CROCUS, reactivity is primarily controlled by adjusting the water level in the vessel, and thus changing the moderating ratio of the core through a spillway system. The water level can be set with an accuracy of ± 0.1 mm, corresponding to a reactivity worth of approximately ± 0.4 pcm near criticality. Reactivity can also be controlled via two optional rods made of B_4C , positioned in symmetrical channels in the outer zone of the core.

The CROCUS reactor has been thoroughly characterized: its geometrical data, material compositions and an exhaustive list of experimental configurations have been accurately determined and compiled into an OECD/NEA international benchmark for reactivity and kinetics parameter calculations [8, 9]. The available experimental data have therefore served as an excellent test-bed for the validation of Monte Carlo simulation codes, particularly with respect to reactivity, kinetic parameters, and reactor period calculations [10–13].

In view of extending this well-established experimental basis, in this work we provide a preliminary investigation of the neutron field in the CROCUS cavity, i.e. the internal space located between the reactor vessel and the concrete shielding. For this purpose, we use a detection apparatus positioned in the cavity at increasing distances from the fuel. The CROCUS cavity, photographed from its entrance, is shown in Fig. 1a, and a CAD-based top view of the surrounding structures is presented in Fig. 1b.

(a)

(b)

Figure 1. Views of the CROCUS vessel and the surrounding structures forming the cavity: (a) Photograph of the CROCUS core, taken from the cavity entrance area, showing the space between the vessel and the concrete shielding. (b) CAD rendering of the structures surrounding the CROCUS core.

In order to reconstruct the neutron flux at different locations in the cavity, we adopted a position-sensitive detector consisting of a proportional counter filled with ^3He gas pressurized to 4 atm, with

a nominal active length of 90 cm. ^3He is widely used for neutron detection, due to its very high thermal neutron absorption cross section (~ 5330 barns) [14]. When a thermal neutron interacts with the gas in the detector, a proton and a tritium nucleus are emitted in opposite directions, with a total kinetic energy of ~ 764 keV [14]. Ideally, these charged particles deposit all their energy in the gas through excitation and ionization, resulting in a single peak in the spectrum. In practice, some ions reach the detector walls before fully depositing their energy. This phenomenon, known as the *wall effect*, leads to partial energy deposition in the detector and produces a continuum in the spectrum, with two threshold values, respectively at ~ 191 keV (when only the tritium nucleus deposits its energy), and ~ 573 keV (when instead only the proton does).

In a position-sensitive ^3He proportional counter, the anode is composed of a resistive material at both ends of the detector. This additional feature allows measuring the charge collected at each end, which enables the determination of the position (P) of a neutron capture event along the detector's active length, using a simple charge-division method [15]. This is formulated as:

$$P = \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{(Q_B - Q_A)}{(Q_A + Q_B)} + 1 \right], \quad (1)$$

where Q_A and Q_B denote the charges collected at ends A and B , respectively. Recording these charges at every neutron interaction allows building an histogram of interaction occurrences as a function of position, thus providing insight into the spatial distribution of the thermal neutron flux within a given region.

3. AXIAL REGION ABOVE THE CORE

The first set of measurements was carried out to characterize the axial profile of the neutron flux in the upper region of the core, from the immediate vicinity of the fuel up to the ceiling of the cavity. For this purpose, the detector was positioned horizontally at three distinct elevations: directly above the fuel rods, with the detector center defined as elevation 0; at an intermediate elevation approximately 45 cm higher; and near the cavity ceiling, about 131 cm above the initial position. The corresponding configurations, each equipped with the detector, are displayed in Fig. 2. As illustrated in Fig. 2a, the detector was positioned to measure the radial neutron flux along the core's central axis. While the active length fully covered the fuel region, mechanical constraints associated with the positioning of the electronic components introduced a slight asymmetry, resulting in a larger fraction of the detector's active volume being located toward the southern side of the CROCUS structure.

Figure 2. Photographs of the ^3He detector positioned horizontally in the three axial elevations investigated for the computation of the neutron distribution in the upper part of the cavity: (a) position 1, with the detector in direct contact with the upper cladding of the fuel rods; (b) position 2, with the detector lifted away from the fuel; (c) position 3, with the detector in the position closest to the ceiling.

The three acquisitions were performed sequentially: the simultaneous use of multiple detectors was deliberately avoided, in order to prevent shadowing effects between adjacent detectors. Each measurement lasted 15 minutes. The water level remained constant during the measurements and was adjusted to reach a critical configuration to maintain a stable neutron flux. The reactor power was kept low (i.e., below 100 mW) for two reasons: first, to ensure a low dose rate for safe access to the cavity in order to reposition the detector; second, to avoid saturation effects in the acquisition chain. For all three acquisitions, a trade-off on the power adjustment was sought, between achieving adequate counting statistics and avoiding detector saturation, with a target count rate of approximately 25 000 cps. The corresponding histograms of neutron interaction positions, reconstructed from the charges collected at the extremities as briefly described in Sec. 2, are shown in Fig. 3a for the three axial positions. A spatial resolution of 5 mm was adopted for constructing the histogram of neutron interaction events. To ensure consistent comparisons between measurements performed at different positions, the histogram data were first normalized to the total acquisition time, yielding count rates in units of counts per second (cps). The resulting values were then scaled by the reactor power, as determined from the CROCUS power monitors using the calibration coefficients reported in Ref. 16. Finally, the data were normalized by the spatial resolution, i.e., the histogram bin width.

Figure 3. Results of the neutron measurements in the upper region of the CROCUS cavity, obtained using a position-sensitive ^3He detector. (a) Count rate (cps) normalized by reactor power in W and spatial resolution in m for the reconstructed histograms of neutron-interaction positions at the three investigated elevations. A graphical legend relates each spatial profile to the corresponding detector position $d_{\text{fuel rods}}$, taken from the fuel. The boundaries of the detector active length covering the fuel region are indicated. (b) Spatial map reconstructed by linear interpolation of the histograms shown in (a). Axial coordinate 0 cm corresponds to the detector in contact with the fuel rods, while coordinate 131 cm corresponds to the highest detector position.

The results concerning the position of neutron interaction events were linearly interpolated to construct a spatial map, illustrated in Fig. 3b. Together with the histograms in Fig. 3a, this map provides insight into the profile of the flux shape along the top portion of the cavity, above the core. For the position closest to the fuel, a bell-shaped distribution centered in the middle of the core is recovered, as expected for a cylindrical core geometry. As the detector is moved away from the fuel, this shape progressively fades out and the profiles flatten. This behavior can be attributed to enhanced neutron scattering from the surrounding structures, including the reactor's wall and the ceiling, both made of concrete, which tends to homogenize the distribution of interaction events within the detector's active volume. Besides altering the flux shape, scattering also influences its magnitude. Indeed, although the distance between positions 2 and 3 is nearly three times that between positions 1 and 2, the number of neutron events

recorded by the detector decreases only slightly between the last two measurements. This observation can be explained by the proximity of the detector in position 3 to the ceiling, where a significant amount of back-scattered neutrons are collected. A minor back-scattering effect from the cavity walls can be observed in the histograms, where the spatial profile shows a slight increase towards the south side. This behavior is consistent with the closer proximity of structural elements that enhance neutron reflection with respect to the north side.

4. RADIAL REGION OUTSIDE THE CORE

The second set of measurements was carried out to characterize the profile of the neutron flux as a function of the radial distance from the core, moving from the direct proximity of the vessel to the wall of the cavity. For this purpose, the north side of the cavity was selected, since it can be easily accessed and there is sufficient space to accommodate the detector and the electronic systems. A dedicated aluminum support structure, shown in Fig. 4a, was designed to hold the detector vertically at several distinct locations, ensuring axial alignment. Each position, marked in red and labeled with its corresponding number in Fig. 4a, was spaced 30 cm apart. This setup allowed measuring of the axial neutron flux at six radial distances from the vessel, ensuring a detailed reconstruction of the neutron distribution in the axial direction, along with a complete characterization of the radial dependence, albeit with a coarser discretization.

Figure 4. Experimental setup for measuring the neutron distribution in the radial region outside the core, from the vessel to the concrete wall on the north side of the cavity. (a) Aluminum structure designed to host the detector in six axially-aligned positions at increasing distances from the reactor core. Each position is numbered, to facilitate comparison of the results. (b) Photograph of the detector in the position closest to the concrete wall, denoted with number 6.

In principle, since the detector's active length is approximately 10 cm shorter than the fuel active height, the axial distribution cannot cover the entire fissile zone, contrary to the case of the analysis of the upper part of the cavity. In order to position the detector, we aligned the upper end with the lower boundary of the core grid, which also serves as the limit for the maximum water level (i.e., 100 cm). This configuration results in the upper boundary of the detector's active part approximately coinciding with the critical water level. Analogously as in the measurements described in Sec. 3, the data acquisitions were carried out sequentially, with each run lasting 15 minutes. The reactor was operated at criticality, to ensure a stable neutron flux, and the power was adjusted for each measurement according to the increasing distance from the core, so as to maintain the detector count rate approximately constant at around 15 000 cps, which provides sufficient counting statistics while avoiding saturation. Higher count

rates could have been targeted, as in Sec. 3; however, constraints related to limiting the reactor power were taken into account in order to allow safe access to the cavity for detector repositioning. Similarly as in the analysis presented in Sec. 3, we reconstructed the histogram of interaction positions and, by linear interpolation, the corresponding spatial map, shown in Fig. 5.

A small ‘bump’ in the neutron flux appears at a position approximately 30 cm below the highest water level in the histogram, and this feature is mirrored in the flux map. However, this peak is likely an artifact related to the detection chain, since it is not observed when using a spare ^3He detector. Further investigations are needed to identify and suppress this artifact. Despite this issue, the results for the spatial map provide valuable insight into the neutron distribution outside the vessel and beyond the water tank.

Figure 5. Results of the reconstruction of the neutron flux in the region outside the vessel using position-sensitive ^3He detectors. (a) Count rate (cps) normalized by reactor power (W) and spatial resolution (m) for the reconstructed histograms of neutron-interaction positions at the six investigated locations at different distances d_{vessel} from the core, defined as the distance from the external vessel diameter. (b) Spatial map of the neutron flux reconstructed by linear interpolation of the histograms shown in (a). The six radial positions investigated, equally spaced by 30 cm, are represented as dashed lines.

Two main features can be identified. The first concerns the radial profile of the axial neutron field. The detector records a neutron distribution that increases from the bottom to the top of the core over approximately 60 cm of the active length, after which a smooth decrease is observed. The slopes of both the rising and falling regions become progressively less steep as the distance from the core increases. This flattening can be attributed to the increased contribution of neutrons back-scattered from the surrounding structures, relative to those arriving directly from the reactor (as already observed in the analysis of the upper part of the cavity), which tends to homogenize the overall spatial distribution of the neutron field. The second feature is observed in the flux profile at position 6, which, although located farthest from the core and therefore expected to yield the lowest magnitude, actually exhibits a neutron count rate comparable to that at position 3 (80 cm from the vessel), and higher than the those at positions 4 (110 cm from the vessel) and 5 (140 cm from the vessel). This behavior, clearly mirrored in the map of Fig. 5b, can be attributed to room-return effects: the detector’s proximity to the concrete wall results in the detection of a significant number of back-scattered neutrons.

5. CONCLUSIONS

We reported the results of a preliminary measurement campaign aimed at characterizing the neutron distribution in the CROCUS cavity, outside the reactor vessel, using a position-sensitive ^3He detector. Measurements were performed both in the upper part of the cavity, at increasing height from the fuel, and in the radial part, from the vessel to the concrete wall of the cavity. The obtained results highlight the strong influence of the surrounding structures on the neutron field, showing that the radial flux shape attenuates rapidly with distance up to a certain point where back-scattering from the walls appears to come into play, leading to slightly increased flux levels just close to the walls.

Overall, our measurements provide a first experimental basis for the characterization of the thermal component of the ex-vessel neutron field, which will serve as reference data for the forthcoming validation of simulation codes, especially in the context of future dismantling and decommissioning studies, where geometrical and mechanical structures play an important role in shaping the neutron distribution in the reactor cavity. Building on this work, future efforts will indeed focus on the detailed modeling of the CROCUS cavity structures using Monte Carlo codes, in view of benchmarking simulation results against experimental measurements. Building on this work, future efforts will indeed focus on the detailed modeling of the CROCUS cavity structures using Monte Carlo codes, in view of benchmarking simulation results against experimental measurements. Furthermore, in order to usefully complement the present results, we will also consider the characterization of the fast component of the neutron field in the cavity.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The valuable help of the CROCUS operations team is gratefully acknowledged.

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